

Codebook

Islamic Finance Bibliometric Corpus — Scopus export (12 Jun 2026)

Corpus size: 1,018 records · Years 2009–2026 · Document type: Article · Language: English · Source: Scopus

1. corpus_metadata.csv — field definitions

Field	Definition
record_id	Unique stable ID: IFnnnn-. Primary key linking the two CSVs.
authors	Author names, Scopus abbreviated form (Surname I.; ...).
title	Article title as exported.
year	Publication year (2009–2026).
source_title	Journal / source name.
volume / issue	Volume and issue numbers (may be blank for early-access).
page_start / page_end	Page range (blank for article-number-only items).
cited_by	Scopus citation count at export date.
doi	Digital Object Identifier (106 records blank).
link	Scopus record URL.
author_keywords	Keywords supplied by authors.
index_keywords	Scopus-assigned index keywords.
document_type	All records = Article.
open_access	Open-access status string from Scopus.
language	Language of original document (all English).
eid	Scopus Electronic ID (unique).
abstract	Full abstract text (0 missing).

2. classification.csv — field definitions

Field	Definition
record_id	Foreign key → corpus_metadata.record_id.
title / year	Carried for coder convenience.
auto_theme	Rule-based theme tag(s) auto-assigned from title/keywords/abstract (see §3). Semicolon-separated; multi-label.
primary_theme	[MANUAL] Single dominant theme assigned by coder.
secondary_theme	[MANUAL] Optional second theme.
method_type	[MANUAL] e.g. empirical-quant / empirical-qual / conceptual / review / mixed.
geographic_focus	[MANUAL] Country or region of study focus.
include_exclude	[MANUAL] Screening decision: include / exclude (+reason).
coder_notes	[MANUAL] Free-text notes.

3. auto_theme rule dictionary

A record receives every theme whose regex patterns match its combined title + author keywords + index keywords + abstract (case-insensitive). Records matching none are tagged 'Unclassified'. These are heuristic starting tags for manual verification, not final classifications.

Theme	Match patterns	Records
Governance & Regulation	governance, regulat*, compliance, legal	485
Maqasid & SDGs	maqasid, sustainab*, SDG, poverty	483
Islamic Banking	islamic/sharia/shariah bank	427
Sukuk & Capital Markets	sukuk, capital market, equity, crowdfund	343
Fintech & Digital	fintech, digital, blockchain, ML, AI	230
Islamic Microfinance	microfinanc*, qard*	137
Waqf & Endowment	waqf, awqaf, endowment	133
Zakat	zakat, zakah	121
Unclassified	(no pattern matched)	30

Note: themes are non-exclusive, so counts sum to more than 1,018.